

EFFECT OF DIGITAL OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study examined the effect of digital operations management on Organizational Sustainability in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to; examine the effect of data management on organizational performance and evaluate the effect of workflow automation on the organizational performance of Southeast Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. A structured questionnaire design with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect data for the study. The data were analyzed using descriptive analysis and sample t-test for the mean comparison in each hypothesis. The result revealed that, at a 5% level of significance, data management has a statistically significant effect on the performance of organizations with a value of $(0.092 > 0.05)$ while workflow automation has a statistically significant effect on the performance of organizations with a value of $(0.000 < 0.05)$ in southeast, Nigeria. We concluded that digital operations management has a significant effect on organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria. We recommended that Organizations should embrace workflow automation solutions to streamline repetitive tasks, minimize manual errors, and enhance operational efficiency. Identify key areas within the organization where automation can yield the most significant impact, such as customer service, inventory management, and supply chain logistics.

Keywords: Digital, Management, Operations, Organizational, Sustainability

1.1 Introduction

In the contemporary landscape of global business, the integration of digital technologies has become a cornerstone of organizational operations, reshaping traditional approaches and redefining the paradigms of efficiency and effectiveness. This transformation, commonly referred to as digital operations management (DOM), encompasses a wide array of digital tools and methodologies aimed at optimizing processes, streamlining workflows, and maximizing resource utilization. Amidst the relentless pursuit of competitive advantage and sustainability, organizations worldwide are increasingly leveraging digitalization as a catalyst for driving not only operational excellence but also long-term viability and resilience. Organizational sustainability, a concept rooted in the principles of balancing economic prosperity, environmental stewardship, and social responsibility, has emerged as a central tenet of contemporary business discourse. Beyond the conventional metrics of financial performance, sustainability encompasses a holistic perspective that considers the interplay between organizational activities and their broader impact on society and the environment. In this context, the effect of digital operations

management on organizational sustainability assumes paramount significance, as it offers the potential to reconcile the imperatives of profitability with the goals of environmental preservation and social equity.

In recent years, the digital revolution has fundamentally reshaped the landscape of business operations across the globe, and South East Nigeria is no exception. As organizations strive to adapt to an increasingly complex and dynamic environment, the integration of digital technologies into their operational frameworks has emerged as a critical strategy for enhancing efficiency, agility, and competitiveness. Against the backdrop of South East Nigeria's evolving economic and business landscape, the impact of digital operations management on organizational sustainability has become a subject of paramount importance. Organizational sustainability, defined as the ability to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, encompasses various dimensions including economic viability, environmental responsibility, and social equity. In this context, the effective deployment of digital technologies holds immense potential to not only drive operational excellence but also to foster long-term sustainability across diverse sectors of the economy.

However, the realization of these benefits is contingent upon a nuanced understanding of the unique challenges and opportunities facing organizations in South East Nigeria. Factors such as infrastructure limitations, skill gaps, regulatory frameworks, and socio-economic dynamics can significantly shape the implementation and outcomes of digital operations management initiatives. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of the interplay between digitalization efforts and organizational sustainability is essential to inform strategic decision-making and policy formulation in the region. This paper seeks to explore the effect of digital operations management on organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Despite the growing importance of digitalization and sustainability in the global business landscape, there is a notable gap in understanding the specific implications and outcomes of digital operations management for organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria. Existing research predominantly focuses on developed economies or broader regional contexts, leaving a significant knowledge deficit regarding the unique challenges and opportunities faced by organizations in this region. South East Nigeria presents a distinct socio-economic, cultural, and institutional context characterized by factors such as infrastructure limitations, skill disparities, regulatory complexities, and socio-political dynamics. Understanding how these contextual factors shape the adoption, implementation, and outcomes of digital operations management initiatives is crucial for developing contextually relevant strategies and interventions to promote organizational sustainability. The key challenge of this study is the lack of data management and workflow automation in Organizational Sustainability in South East Nigeria. Addressing these research challenges requires an interdisciplinary approach that draws on insights from management, information technology, sustainability science, economics, sociology, and public policy. By elucidating the complexities of the effect of digital operations management on organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria, research endeavors can contribute to informed decision-making, policy formulation, and practice implementation aimed at fostering sustainable development and resilience in the region.

1.3 Objective of the study

The study's main objective is to examine the effect of digital operations management on Organizational Sustainability in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are

- i. To examine the effect of data management on the organizational performance of Southeast Nigeria
- ii. To evaluate the effect of workflow automation on the organizational performance of Southeast Nigeria

1.4 Hypotheses of the Study

- i. Data management has no significant effect on the organizational performance of Southeast Nigeria
- ii. Workflow automation has no significant effect on the organizational performance of East Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Digital Operations Management

Digital Operations Management (DOM) aims to enhance and streamline corporate processes by utilizing digital technologies and data-driven methodologies. It includes a broad range of actions meant to boost productivity, adaptability, and general performance across different organizational functions. Digitalization is quickly becoming an important driver of environmental, social, and governance management (ESGM). Modern advances in digital technology enable companies to implement and communicate their environmental, social, and good governance practices through digital platforms. The goal of digital operations management is to employ digital technologies to optimize company processes. To maximize business operations, digital operations management includes the design, execution, and oversight of digital technology and procedures. It entails utilizing automation, data analytics, digital tools, and other technology to optimize workflows, boost productivity, and raise overall performance. Organizations can respond swiftly to shifting consumer tastes, market situations, and competitive demands thanks to DOM. Organizations may expedite innovation, optimize development processes, and provide value to consumers more quickly by implementing agile approaches like DevOps. The goal of digital operations management is to use digital technology to improve agility, promote operational excellence, and provide value to clients. Organizations can position themselves for success in the current digital economy by embracing digital transformation and using a data-driven approach (Gupta, 2020; Bharadwaj et al 2013).

Data Management

Data management is the practice of collecting, organizing, and accessing data to support productivity, efficiency, and decision-making. Data management is a crucial first step to employing effective data analysis at scale, which leads to important insights that add value to your customers and improve your bottom line. With effective data management, people across an organization can find and access trusted data for their queries. Data management can increase the visibility of your organization's data assets, making it easier for people to quickly and confidently find the right data for their analysis, (Chinyere and Ikoromasoma 2021). Data visibility allows your company to be more organized and productive, allowing employees to find the data they need to better do their jobs. Data management is a crucial piece of deploying the information technology systems that run business applications and provide analytical information to help derive operational decision-making and strategic planning by corporate executives, business managers, and other end users. Data is seen as a corporate asset that can be used to make more informed business decisions, improve marketing campaigns, optimize business operations, and reduce costs,

all to increase revenue and profits (Jack 2019). However, a lack of proper data management systems can saddle organizations with incompatible data that can affect the organization's performance.

An efficient and effective data management system helps minimize potential errors and reduce the damages caused by bad data. Therefore, an effective data management strategy must be implemented to better control the most valuable asset of the business. Managing data as a resource is an important managerial task in any organization today. Business success depends not only on the possession of resources but on the efficient utilization of resources, data, and information within an organization and its environment form part of the strategic, tactical, and operational resources of an enterprise (Lessing & Scheepers 2001). Data management system results in a reduction of time to find necessary information which increases employee performance. Data management is a crucial first step to employing effective data analysis at scale, which leads to important insights that add value to your customers and improve your bottom line. With effective data management, people across an organization can find and access trusted data for their queries. Some benefits of an effective data management solution include:

- a. Visibility
- b. Reliability
- c. Security
- d. Scalability
- e. Sustainability

Workflow Automation

Workflow automation is an approach to making the flow of tasks, documents and information across work-related activities perform independently by defined business rules. Workflow is a series of activities needed to complete a task. Workflow automation shifts the performance of those activities from humans to a software program. To automate a workflow, an organization first identifies the tasks that make up the job. It next creates the rules and logic that govern how those tasks should be done. Finally, it programs the software with predefined business rules and logic. Workflow automation is important for high-value tasks, savings, visibility, communication, customer service advantages, product quality, and performance tracking of organizations. These attributes are important because they boost an organization's ability to compete in the digital era. Organizations across all industries can benefit from workflow automation. Moreover, they can use this technology in various departments and niche areas such as supporting DevOps workflows within the IT department.

The following examples illustrate the applicability of workflow automation in industries and departments:

- a. **Health:** Medical providers use workflow automation to generate staff work schedules and on-call rotations. Providers also use these tools to support patient admission and discharge and to transfer patients' electronic health records.
- b. **Legal.** Whether in the legal industry itself or the legal function within an enterprise, workflow automation is used to automate billing, input new client information, submit and track contract reviews, and manage case deadlines.
- c. **Information technology.** IT departments use automation to support DevOps teams and other groups.

- d. Financial.** Financial businesses and groups within an enterprise use workflow automation for data entry and account approval processes.
- e. Marketing.** Workflow automation can help with various aspects of marketing automation, making tasks associated with brand management and campaigns happen automatically in a prescribed order.
- f. Sales.** These departments often automate the approval of proposals and quotes, the introduction of salespeople to leads generated through website interactions, and the generation of a task list once a lead schedules a meeting with a sales rep.
- g. Cyber security.** Workflow automation speeds incident response, making the process more efficient.
- h. Human resources.** Automation facilitates various HR processes, such as time sheet approvals, onboarding and off-boarding employees, and managing personnel changes.
- i. Operations.** Workflow automation is used for a multitude of tasks, including compiling reports and assigning tasks.

Organizational Sustainability

The ability of an organization to persevere over time while preserving or enhancing its relevance, impact, and performance in the face of diverse internal and external obstacles is referred to as organizational sustainability. Organizational sustainability addresses the long-term viability and resilience of an organization across economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Organizational sustainability often focuses on environmental, social, and economic factors. Sustainability is a prerequisite for companies to survive in today's market. Sustainability, like digital transformation, necessitates organizational restructuring. Prioritizing sustainability helps with investor demands, customer demands, regulatory requirements, talent acquisition, and productivity increases. Savitz and Weber (2006), the term "triple bottom line" refers to the economic, environmental, and social aspects of sustainability:

Economic Sustainability: This facet pertains to the organization's resiliency and sound financial standing. It entails bringing in money, effectively controlling expenses, and guaranteeing sustained profitability. To survive swings in the economy, economic sustainability also entails careful financial planning, innovation investment, and income source diversification, (Smith, 2020).

Environmental Sustainability: Businesses must cut back on resource use, waste production, and pollution emissions to lessen their impact on the environment. This entails implementing sustainable practices in the design of products and services, procurement, and operations. Initiatives like energy efficiency, the utilization of renewable resources, and trash reduction/recycling programs are also included in the category of environmental sustainability.

Social Sustainability: Promoting positive relationships with stakeholders, including as workers, clients, vendors, local communities, and society at large, is a key component of social sustainability. It means upholding fair labor practices, upholding human rights, encouraging diversity, equity, and inclusion inside the company, and supporting community development. Transparency in communication and ethical corporate practices are also components of social sustainability.

A comprehensive strategy that incorporates these elements into strategic planning, decision-making procedures, and daily operations is needed to achieve organizational sustainability. Meeting new opportunities and challenges entails establishing precise goals, evaluating performance with pertinent indicators, and continuously enhancing procedures. Additionally, sustaining sustainability and fostering resilience in the face of uncertainty requires cooperation with stakeholders, flexibility in response to changing conditions, and a long-term outlook, (Ameer and Othman 2012).

Organizational performance

Organizational performance refers to the degree to which the organization, with some informational, financial, and human resources, positions itself effectively in the business market. More so, it is a set of financial and non-financial signs or pointers to assessing the levels to which organizational goals and objectives have been attained (Kaplan & Norton, 1992). Wiig (1995) defined performance as the process of quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of an organization's action. It is the process of assessing the progress made (actual) towards achieving predetermined set goals. It involves the establishment of organizational goals, monitoring progress toward the goals, and making necessary modifications to attain those goals effectively and efficiently (Richard et al 2009). Griffin (2003) described organizational performance as the extent to which the organization can meet the needs of its stakeholders and its own survival needs.

This formulation broadened the concept of organizational performance beyond strictly market-focused measures such as profit margin, market share, or product quality, all of which are important to certain stakeholders and overall organizational survival, to include several other nonfinancial factors. Organizational performance reflects the ability of an organization to fulfill its shareholders' desires and survive in the market. Also, organizational performance is known as the outcome of the actions or activities, that members of organizations carry out to measure how well an organization has accomplished its objectives (Chung, R-G., and Lo, 2007; Ho, 2008). So, organizational performance is the ability of the organization to achieve its goals. Goal achievement is one of the essential criteria to identify the performance of an organization. Organizational performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes: (a) financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.); (b) product market performance (sales, market share, etc.); and (c) shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc.).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The Theory of Performance Frontiers

The theory of performance frontiers provides us with a clearer understanding of when the laws of trade-offs and cumulative capabilities apply. The theory suggests that a plant that operates near its asset performance frontier will reap greater benefits from structural, and technological changes than other plants. A performance frontier is therefore defined by the maximum performance that can be achieved by a manufacturing unit given a set of operating choices. These types of changes usually require a large investment of resources to move the frontier or change its shape. Plants that are not near their frontiers are not likely to enjoy as high returns on these investments because the frontier is largely irrelevant to them. Instead, a plant in this condition would benefit more from a

cumulative improvement approach aimed at improving infrastructure and operating efficiencies (such as quality-related improvements), (Schmenner and Swink, 1998).

The Theory of Swift, Even Flow

The Theory of Swift, Even Flow holds that the swifter and even the flow of materials through a process, the more productive that process is. Thus, productivity for any process – be it labor productivity, machine productivity, materials productivity, or total factor productivity rises with the speed by which materials flow through the process, and it falls with increases in the variability associated with the flow, be that variability associated with the demand on the process or with steps in the process itself. The Theory of Swift, Even Flow is thus consistent with the deductive laws of variability and of bottlenecks, and its measures of throughput time and variability are easily understood (Schmenner and Swink, 1998).

2.3 Empirical Review

Wong and Ngin (1997) conducted a study on the impact of production automation on the organizational performance of electronics manufacturing firms in Singapore. The study aims to evaluate the impact of production automation on the four dimensions of organizational performance identified as operational performance, labor management effectiveness, workers' well-being, and remuneration. A survey design was used for this study. The results revealed that automation was perceived to have resulted in greater improvements in operational performance and worker's well-being than in labor-management effectiveness and workers' remuneration.

Awan and Khan (2016) conducted a study to investigate the impact of management information systems on the performance of different organizations in Pakistan. The study aims to show how management information systems have a positive impact on the performance of the organization and how they can increase the profitability, innovation, and growth of the organization. Questionnaire and Descriptive statistics were used for this study. The results revealed that there is a positive relationship between the performance of the organization and the management information system.

Chinyere and Ikoromasoma (2021) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between data management systems and the organizational efficiency of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The study aims to assess the relationship between the data management system and organizational efficiency and the relationship between the data management system and cost reduction of the deposit money bank in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The result revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between data management systems and the organizational efficiency of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt.

Bayode (2023) conducted a study on the effect of automation on organizational structure, job performance, and communication in university libraries in South West, Nigeria. The study aims to identify the automation status of university libraries, determine the functional areas in which automation has been implemented in university libraries, ascertain the impact of automation on the organizational structure, determine the impact of automation on the job performance of the staff, ascertain the impact of automation on the communication and determine the constraints to automation in university libraries in South West, Nigeria. The survey research design was used. The

results revealed that automation has enabled a more flexible working environment, affected the pattern of staffing by specialization, and bridged the gap between communication flow through the use of a variety of information and technology communication (ICT) tools.

3. Methodology

A descriptive survey design will be utilized for the study. This research design is concerned with the description of data and characteristics of a population. The goal is to acquire factual, accurate, and systematic data and describe the data and characteristics studied. It is also useful because of the relatively large population from which the information was collected. The study was conducted in 3 selected organizations across southeast Nigeria, known as DataXpress Professionals, Globeet Data Limited, and Collette Enterprise which are all located in Nigeria. The choice for these firms was attributed to the integrity they have built especially in the area of accounting in Nigeria over the years.

Study Population

The population of the study is specifically are staff of DataXpress Professionals, Globeet Data Limited, and Collette Enterprise. The study population comprised all the staff working with these selected organizations. The total population of the staff was obtained from the human resource department of the firms as shown in below table 1.

Table 1: Study Population

Organization	Population	N (%)
DataXpress Professionals	56	43.8%
Globeet Data Limited	42	32.8%
Collette Enterprise	30	23.4%
TOTAL	128	100%

Source: Human Resources Mgt

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

This study is based on a confidence level of 95 percent. Hence, the level of significance for the study was determined as follows:

The level of Significance is stated below in equation (1)

$$\frac{100 \text{ confidence level}}{100} = \frac{100 - 95}{100} = 0.05 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The sample size for the study was determined using Yamane's (1973) formula for sample size determination. The sample was calculated from the population of the study to determine a sample size that is representative of the population size. The formula is as follows in equation (2)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where n is the sample size

N = The population of the study

e= level of significance (margin of tolerable error)

1 = constant

Hence,

$$n = \frac{128}{1 + 128(0.5)^2} = 96.96$$

Therefore, the sample size is approximately 97

Data were gathered in the chosen organizations in southeast Nigeria using a self-administered questionnaire. A response rate of 86.6 percent was obtained from 84 out of 97 respondents who returned the questionnaire. Demographic inquiries on respondents' gender, age, level of education, and position or role made up the first section of the form. Likert scales with five points were used in the construction of the instrument's second section. This section involved the measurement of the study variables using a well-designed measurement item concerning each of the research objectives. All the data were analyzed using descriptive analysis and sample t-test for the mean comparison in each hypothesis. All the information and identity of the respondent were treated as confidential and used for learning purposes only.

4. RESULTS

Frequency Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Analysis (156)

Profile	Category	Frequency (N)	Percent (%)
Gender			
	Male	35	42%
	Female	49	58%
Age			
	<24yrs	08	10%
	24-33yrs	21	25%
	34-43yrs	33	39%
	44-53yrs	18	21%
	>53yrs	04	5%
Education			
	Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE)	===	
	NCE/OND	===	
	HND/BSC	67	80%
	Postgraduate certificate	17	20%
Position/Role			
	Junior Staff	39	46%
	Middle-class staff	26	31%
	Senior Staff	19	23%

Table 1 presents that most of the respondents were female (58%) and the majority of the respondents were between 34-43 years old having a (39%) response rate of the entire sample. More than half of the respondents were HND/BSC holders (80%) and the majority of the respondents were in the junior staff bracket with a (46%) response rate.

Reliability Analysis

Table 2: Reliability Analysis table

Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
Items used for Objective One	5	0.757
Items used for objective two	5	0.721

Table 2 shows that all the variables adopted in this study had Cronbach’s Alpha value of more than 0.70. This indicated that the items used to measure the variables were reliable and consistent (Hair, 2006).

Descriptive Analysis

Table 3: To examine the effect of data management on the performance of organizations in Southeast Nigeria

S/n	Measurement Items	Mean	SD
1	Data security measures are effectively implemented in our organization.	3.002	1.004
2	Employees receive adequate training on data handling and security protocols.	3.214	1.032
3	Data management practices in our organization comply with relevant regulatory requirements.	3.331	0.541
4	The availability of accurate and reliable data positively impacts our organizational decision-making.	3.139	1.129
5	Data analytics tools and technologies are effectively utilized to derive insights for business growth.	3.443	1.563
	Aggregate Mean	3.2258	1.0538

Table 4: To evaluate the effect of workflow automation on the organization's performance in Southeast Nigeria.

S/n	Measurement Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Workflow automation has enhanced collaboration among team members.	3.786	0.547
2	Workflow automation has improved the overall quality of our products/services.	3.341	0.811
3	Employees find workflow automation easy to use and understand.	3.086	0.187
4	Automation has helped us meet deadlines and deliverables more consistently.	3.674	1.576
	Aggregate Mean	3.4717	0.7803

Tables 3 and 4 are the descriptive analysis of the responses from the participants about objectives one and two respectively. The results suggest that the participants agree with the formulated question items, this is evident based on the mean of each item which is significantly higher than the minimum acceptable mean of 3.0.

Tests of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H01: Data management has no significant effect on the performance of organizations in Southeast Nigeria
The mean scores from Table 3 were used for testing this hypothesis.

Table 5: T-test result of mean comparison of items from research question one

Table 5: One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
H0 ₁	5	3.2258	1.0538	.13129

Table 6: One-Sample Test

Test Value = 3.0						
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
H0 ₁	4.007	4	.001	.2258	-.0632	.5532

Source: SPSS, Version 28.0

Interpretation and Decision

The analysis in Table 6 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of significance level was 0.092, which is greater than 0.05. This implies that it was significant. In other words, the null hypothesis should be accepted.

Decision:

At a 5% level of significance, data management has a statistically significant effect on the performance of organizations in southeast, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H02: Workflow automation has no significant effect on the performance of organizations in southeast Nigeria
The mean scores from Table 4 were used for testing this hypothesis.

Table 7: T-test result of mean comparison of items from research question one

Table 7: One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
H0 ₂	4	3.4717	.7803	.12489

Table 8: One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 3.0					
		Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
H0 ₂	6.236	3	.000	.4717	.0774	.6978

Source: SPSS, Version 28.0

Interpretation and Decision

The analysis in Table 8 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of significance level was 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This implies that it was significant. In other words, the null hypothesis should be rejected.

Decision:

At a 5% level of significance; workflow automation has a statistically significant effect on the performance of organizations in southeast, Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of digital operations management on organizational sustainability in southeast, Nigeria with the following objectives;

1. To examine the effect of data management on the performance of organizations in southeast, Nigeria.
2. To evaluate the effect of workflow automation on the performance of organizations in southeast, Nigeria.

The results as stated in Tables 6 and 8 suggest that for hypothesis one, at a 5% level of significance data management has a significant effect on the performance of the organizations in southeast, Nigeria. For hypothesis two at a 5% level of significance workflow automation has a statistically significant effect on the performance of organizations in southeast, Nigeria.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the effect of digital operations management on organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria is unequivocal. Through meticulous data management and streamlined workflow automation, organizations in this region have witnessed remarkable enhancements in their overall performance and sustainability. The efficient utilization of digital tools and technologies has enabled businesses to optimize their resources, minimize operational inefficiencies, and adapt swiftly to dynamic market conditions.

Data management emerges as a critical factor in driving organizational success, facilitating informed decision-making, and fostering a culture of accountability and transparency within enterprises. By harnessing data-driven insights, businesses can identify areas for improvement, capitalize on emerging opportunities, and mitigate risks effectively. Moreover, robust data management practices lay the foundation for innovation and strategic growth, empowering organizations to stay ahead of the curve in a competitive landscape.

Similarly, the adoption of workflow automation has revolutionized the operational landscape of South East Nigeria, empowering organizations to streamline processes, enhance productivity, and deliver superior customer experiences. By automating routine tasks and optimizing workflows, businesses can allocate resources more efficiently, minimize errors, and accelerate time-to-market for products and services. This agility not only enhances organizational performance but also strengthens resilience in the face of external disruptions, ensuring sustained success in the long run. We concluded that digital operations management has a significant effect on organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria

Recommendation

In light of the significant impact that digital operations management, particularly data management and workflow automation, has on organizational sustainability in South East Nigeria, businesses in the region must prioritize the adoption and integration of these technologies into their operational frameworks. To maximize the benefits and drive sustainable growth, the following recommendations are offered:

- i. Organizations should prioritize investment in robust data management systems capable of collecting, storing, and analyzing data efficiently. This includes implementing modern data analytics tools and technologies to derive actionable insights from the vast amounts of data generated within the organization. Additionally, emphasis should be placed on data security measures to safeguard sensitive information and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.
- ii. Organizations should embrace workflow automation solutions to streamline repetitive tasks, minimize manual errors, and enhance operational efficiency. Identify key areas within the organization where automation can yield the most significant impact, such as customer service, inventory management, and supply chain logistics. Implement tailored automation solutions that align with the specific needs and objectives of the business, considering factors such as scalability, integration capabilities, and ease of maintenance.

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